

IMPROVEMENT OF THE AUDIT OF LEASING TRANSACTIONS THROUGH THE USE OF THE METHOD OF EXTRAPOLATION

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Abstract. This article examines the methods of selective audit, such as extrapolation and stratification. The effectiveness of the use of extrapolation in the audit of credit and leasing companies has been studied and proved mathematically. Conclusions are also drawn and solutions are proposed for effective and correct audit results.

Key words: extrapolation method, stratification method, audit sample, international financial reporting standards, lessor's audit, lessee's audit.

INTRODUCTION

The company conducts economic operations to maintain the continuity of its business. Business operations in the company depend on each other. These operations are presented by management in the form of davriy financial statements. Thus, the management can annually see the results of the financial statements of the company, whether they increase or decrease.

In a nutshell, the embodiment of accounting information that is important to the company in financial statements shows useful information for making decisions in the future. The financial report contains various elements such as income, property, building, construction, equipment and others. One of the elements contained in the financial report under the Section " long-term assets " is the basic instruments. Since fixed assets are long-term assets, they have high value in most companies.

To the effect of the financial statement, the underlying instruments constitute the largest amount in the indication of the total assets of the company.

In assessing the reliability of a financial statement, an independent audit

service is needed by companies and is conducted to verify that the financial statement is in compliance with IFRS.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Russian scientist Kerimov V.E. proceeding from the history of leasing, he described the meaning of leasing as follows: "leasing is a financial activity for obtaining property under a contract between individuals or legal entities with a certain payment on these specific terms."

The first company to carry out financial lease agreements in France was established in 1957 year ("Sepafites" s 1962 g. - "Locafrance"), in 1960 in Great Britain ("Mercantile Leasing Company "v kachestve sovместnogo predpriyatiya" Mercantil Credit Company "i" United States Leasing Corporation"), in 1962 in Germany ("Mietfinanzierung GmbH"), in 1969 in Japan ("Century Leasing System"). The use of rental services in the US and the West has become popular with the advent of Railways, which has been improved. In half of the XX century, leased trains, planes, water ships began to be built. In particular, the implementation of rent circulation through agreements by commercial banks on the basis of the normative legal framework was improved. Relations in the sphere of rent in foreign countries are based on different types of factors, both on the legal and administrative basis. In some countries, there are normative legal grounds for controlling rent circulation, while in some countries these rent circulation are not normative legal grounds. To date, any circulation of rent is manifested in the lease agreement on a normative legal basis through agreements. For example, in the United States, the single trade Code of rent circulation provides for the normative legal basis. And in Canada, rental transactions are normalized by the Civil Code.

In particular, on December 25, 1995 by the decision of the Oliy Majlis of the

Republic of Uzbekistan the first part of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and on August 29, 1996 the second part of this code was approved. The sixth paragraph of Article 34 of the civil code is devoted to leasing, that is, to financial leasing, in which the definition of leasing is given, consisting of a total of 13 articles, this paragraph covers the lease agreement, the object, the subject, the lease payments, the obligations, responsibilities, rights of the parties and a number of other issues.

METHODOLOGY

This article uses the methods of analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, grouping, financial analysis of scientific knowledge.

The requirements of this standard, during the implementation of an audit that does not provide for the preparation of an official audit opinion on its results, as well as during the provision of peer services (consulting services) to the audit, are subject to a recommendation. In cases when the specific task is excluded from the mandatory requirements of this standard during the execution, the audit organization must do so in its working documents and in a mandatory manner in a written report to the management of the audit and (or) the economic entity that issued the order to it for related services.

One of the differences between the rules of national and international standards of auditing is that there are different wording of the objectives of applying the analytical procedures. In accordance with the International audit Standard 520 "analytical practices", the auditor's purpose of using analytical practices is to::

- thorough practical analysisillarni obtaining relevant and reliable audit evidence in performance;

-the development and conduct of analytical procedures closer to the end of the audit will help the auditor to form a general conclusion on the appropriateness of financial statements to the auditor's understanding of the organization.

1-picture. Features of audited

International standards on auditing require reasonable assurance that the financial statements of the person being audited from it are free from material misstatement even due to fraud and error in order to substantiate the opinion of the auditor during the audit.

AXS 200" the main objective of an independent auditor in conducting an audit in accordance with international auditing standards " reasonable assurance is achieved when the auditor has adequate relevant auditing evidence to reduce the risk of the auditor.

Uniform requirements for random checks in the audit, as well as methods of selection of audited elements for the purpose of collecting audit evidence. The main reason for resorting to selective control during the Audit is the high complexity of

the control procedures. In planning the audit, the principle of random inspection is envisaged. However, during the audit process, continuous inspections, which are usually carried out for the most important items, can also be used.

In selective audit, the following methods are used:

Extrapolation is the transfer of conclusions made about any part of objects or phenomena to a whole complex of these objects or phenomena, as well as other parts of them.

Table 1

ORDORDJES RULES IN THE CALCULATION OF EXTRAPOLATION¹

N ^o	sum	N ^o	sum
1	3820	13	6660
2	9470	14	5490
3	3490	15	5980
4	7790	16	6250
5	4210	17	83900
6	3870	18	3630
7	4490	19	6090
8	9620	20	10450
9	6200	21	6800
10	6350	22	6470
11	7430	23	9160
12	7670	24	5110

N ^o	Excel Formula	Poison
1	= LOG10 (24)	1,38
2	= 1 + 3,322 × 1,38	5,58
3	=WHOLE (5,58)	5
4	= (10 450 – 3 490) / 5	1 392

Interval	Range
1	3 490–4 882
2	4 882–6 274
3	6 274–7 666
4	7 666–9 058
5	9 058–10 450

Stratification is the process of dividing the gross general audit process into

¹ American statistics economist Gerbert Styordjes (Herbert Arthur Sturges, 1882-1958).

small groups, each of which differs from each other by similar characteristics of its constituent units;

Extrapolation method bugunda audit conducted by chillelanilaetgan eng samarali cardan biranda. The foil is based on the folk method of standard audit ontkazacilayetgan heat standard inaklarga yarat gilaseng gamlar, yobi izhorbank, acting as a whole or biror-the power of beryroliya turigida the probability that yovtotishni koplasha purposefully organized kilinadisv reservalar.

The intellarga standard Yarat gijzaligan reservlar tejour banklari tomatir soliklar and the tower of majburiy dllandan suchng kovshgan sof foida counted the overall yigili viligi the appropriate decision to organize cardinadi.

Leasing of audit portfolios of smokers of the heat of ice extrusion banking method of heat intensity fruit. James boo methods of orcaling audit roasting for a long time deskin book-Olib Keladi. Literally crane nisklangan jonotishlarni koplash resources arkali kaytarmaslik probably Yukori bulgan plateau zharatmalar vilinishi. Ushbu azhratma prompted the lessee to provide a large enterprise renabelika vozhazhay.

Business thinking, extrusion, is not preferably based on the use of the pension method of public audit, but rather the audience is functionally long-term. Bundan thirst, resourcelarni formatted keitarilmaslik probably daritai yukor bulgan navllarari uchun "entrepreneur bankida activlar nullatini classifier and activlar buyi likely and yonotishni kopyash mochun resources scopullar forms a pseudonym in the working demise to correlate the purpose of Heb-dismemberment.

The auditor is faster than the audience, the auditor is eney engillashich and the optimalatyrichy uhun auditlik sitlacing of the ishlab chorikadi standard and methodologies. And the standardlarning of each beri yzining afllelari and

kamchiliklarig ego bulganligi blamed the reasons, turli dolinshuvlaylash conditionality corresponds to the photo ettirishni recommended Estadi.

Audit of the heat called tanlab from the shape of the valleys of Ta-vilochandisti Shi-amillar damaged kuzidasatyeddy: shvazigan Audi hajimi and value, Ishi control trahalling condition, tanlab tool dolingus-tensioning anukligi, kutaetgan hatolik and Bosch.

- **The advantages of statistical** selection include the possibility of calculating the size of the selection, the control over the degree of error in the selection, the accuracy of the results of selection through extrapolation in the audit process, and the degree of reduction in the level of certain risks.
- **Non-statistical** elective studies are usually based on the professional opinion of the auditor. The disadvantages of non-statistical selection are as follows:
 - it is not possible to determine the size of the minimum selection audit work required to achieve the objective;
 - the errors detected in the non-statistical sampling type during the audit process are equal to the entire investigated group taqsimlash.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The main methods used in the selection of elements for selective auditing research are random sampling, systematic selection.
2. Since the purpose of forming any audited audit is to characterize the total gross/(gross) (with a certain error), any audited audit must be either statistical or non-statistical.
3. The choice of a nonstatist is used to obtain only one result and does not allow to make a mathematically accurate prediction to confirm its properties.
4. It is unsuitable for evaluating the results of selection methods by statistical

methods. However, the auditor is able to apply methods of impossibility, often objectively, but complex probability methods exceed the effect of using costs.

In accordance with the purpose of using this model for leasing enterprises in economic entities, 1000 leases were received from buyers and 5 of them were fully examined and the international standards were considered to be reserve in AOSIS and the same present rate was spread out to the buyers of the Obsidian lease under the extrapolation model.

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